

Per-Channel Quantile Fullgrid Probing for Small Language Model Observation

Chen Ho Yiing (Norika Oda)
Independent Researcher
ORCID: 0009-0006-6816-9891

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Abstract

We describe a dense activation probing protocol for small to mid-sized language models that operates within a fixed cell budget while maintaining high observation coverage. The protocol combines per-channel quantile binning, an expanded calibration probe corpus ($P = 1200$), and an additive shard merge step that allows heterogeneous compute resources to contribute. Across thirteen runs spanning seven model families and parameter counts from 124M to 7.6B, the protocol reaches at least 90.6 percent coverage on every run, with a median of 94.95 percent and a maximum of 97.05 percent. Per-channel binning combined with a larger probe budget was associated with higher coverage compared to earlier pooled-bin, smaller-corpus configurations on the same models, but the isolated contribution of each factor remains untested in this draft. One within-model comparison point (Qwen-3B at $P = 180$ with pooled binning and shrunk $Q = 6$) suggests that probe corpus expansion alone is not strictly necessary to qualify. A controlled 2x2 ablation is the recommended next experiment. The pipeline is organized for reproducibility and can be released alongside the run artifacts. It runs on commodity hardware.

Keywords: dense activation probing, per-channel quantiles, distributed mechanistic interpretability, model observation, methodology

1 Motivation

A companion methodology paper (*Coverage Failure as a Diagnostic Signal in Neural Model Probing*) shows that satisfying a cell-count threshold is not equivalent to producing a useful dense activation grid. In a multi-machine probing study of nineteen small to mid-sized language models, runs with the same nominal cell budget produced coverage values ranging from 58.75% to 97.05% depending on the protocol.

Two protocol choices drove that gap. First, the use of per-channel quantile binning rather than a single quantile vector pooled across all output channels of a module. Second, the size of the probe corpus used both for calibrating quantile edges and for filling the heat grid. This paper documents the protocol that produced the high-coverage runs and characterizes the operational properties of the protocol on real heterogeneous hardware.

2 Protocol

2.1 Grid definition

For each model the heat grid is a dense `uint32` tensor indexed by four axes:

- module index m (every `nn.Linear` and matching `Conv1D` submodule that is reached by the forward pass on any probe input; optionally also normalization layers when `include_norms` is set)
- channel index c within that module’s output dimension
- quantile bucket q (0 to $Q - 1$)
- sequence position bucket s (0 to $S - 1$)

Q and S are computed per model so that the grid contains at least `target_cells = 1e8` cells, given the model’s actual module count and channel widths.

2.2 Per-channel quantile binning

For each (module, channel) pair we compute $Q + 1$ quantile edges from a calibration sample. Activation values during the heat-fill pass are then digitized against the channel’s own edges. This contrasts with the pooled variant in which one edge vector is shared across all channels in a module.

Pooled binning is faster but assumes channels share an activation distribution. In practice channels in a Transformer linear projection have very different scales and supports, especially when residual streams are present. Pooled binning concentrates counts in a few buckets of channels with large activations and leaves other channels’ buckets empty. Per-channel binning corrects this at the cost of additional memory for the edges ($Q + 1$ floats per channel rather than per module) and additional compute per cell.

2.3 Two-pass execution

Our pipeline has two passes over the probe corpus:

1. **Calibration pass.** Forward each probe through the model with hooks attached to every observed module. From each hook record per-channel activation samples, capped at `calibration-rows-per-module` to bound memory. After the pass, compute per-channel quantile edges and write `quantile_edges.npz` to disk.
2. **Heat-fill pass.** Forward each probe again, this time using the edges to digitize activations and increment heat counts.

Separating the two passes allows the edges to be reused across multiple heat-fill shards.

2.4 Shardable additive heat

Heat counts are additive across probe subsets. To parallelize, we partition the probe corpus into `shard_count` groups and run the heat-fill pass on each group on a separate worker. Each worker writes a shard directory containing its `grid.npy`. A single merge host then sums the shards element-wise to produce the final grid.

This allows heterogeneous machines to contribute. A fast worker can take multiple shards while a slow worker takes one. Calibration is performed once and the same `quantile_edges.npz` is copied to every worker.

Neither model loading nor the calibration pass is parallelized. Both run once per model on whichever machine has enough RAM to hold the weights.

2.5 Calibration corpus

The calibration corpus and the heat-fill corpus are the same set of P probes. The choice of P trades calibration fidelity against wall time.

In the runs reported in this paper, $P = 1200$. The probes are drawn from a mix of English and Chinese natural-language prompts, code, structured data, mathematics, and short instruction-following queries. The exact corpus is the file `probes_1200.txt` referenced in our distributed runbook.

3 Results

3.1 Coverage on the production protocol

Thirteen runs were executed on the protocol described above (per-channel quantiles, $P = 1200$, `include_norms=True`, `bfloat16`, `target_cells=1e8`). One additional run on `qwen-3b` (at $Q = 6$, $S = 15$, $P = 180$, pooled binning) reached the qualification threshold despite using the older configuration; that point is shown for contrast.

Table 1: Qualified runs under the production protocol, sorted by coverage ascending.

Run	Params	Cells	Coverage
qwen-3b (Q=6,S=15,P=180)	3B	106,571,520	90.64%
internlm2-7b	7B	146,880,000	90.87%
qwen2.5-7b	7B	154,265,600	94.15%
bloomz-3b	3B	110,080,000	94.18%
bloomz-560m	560M	102,559,744	94.32%
pythia-2.8b	2.8B	104,938,240	94.38%
qwen-3b	3B	118,412,800	94.88%
qwen2.5-3b	3B	118,412,800	94.95%
bloom-3b	3B	110,080,000	95.46%
bloomz-1b1	1.1B	102,875,136	95.85%
bloom-560m	560M	102,559,744	95.91%
bloom-1b1	1.1B	102,875,136	96.75%
phi-2	2.7B	105,628,160	97.05%

Median coverage 94.95 percent. Minimum 90.64 percent. Maximum 97.05 percent. Every run satisfies the dual criterion of `actual_cells` $\geq 1e8$ and `coverage_pct` ≥ 90 .

3.2 Comparison against earlier protocols on the same models

The same target models had previously been observed under two earlier protocols. Three of those earlier runs (GPT-2 124M, GPT-2-medium 355M, Gemma-2-2B-it) appear in the companion paper’s full table. Two additional comparison points come from Qwen-3B:

Table 2: Same-model protocol comparison on Qwen-3B.

Model	Protocol	Cells	Coverage
Qwen-3B	$P = 180$, pooled	118,412,800	87.08%
Qwen-3B	$P = 1200$, per-channel	118,412,800	94.88%
Qwen-3B	$Q = 6, S = 15, P = 180$, pooled	106,571,520	90.64%

Holding the model fixed, the protocol change from ($P = 180$, pooled) to ($P = 1200$, per-channel) closes the coverage gap by 7.8 percentage points. The compromise protocol ($Q = 6, S = 15, P = 180$, pooled) just reaches qualification by shrinking Q to concentrate counts.

We interpret this as evidence that the protocol, not the model, controlled coverage in our earlier runs. We do not, with the current data, separate the per-channel binning contribution from the $P = 1200$ contribution. Two observations bound the question:

- The ($Q = 6, S = 15, P = 180$, pooled) run shows that pooled binning can reach 90.64% coverage if Q is shrunk and S is adjusted. So per-channel binning is not strictly necessary to pass at 90 percent.
Note that achieving qualification via shrunk Q trades resolution for fill: with $Q = 6$ each channel only has six quantile buckets, which makes detection of subtle activation patterns harder downstream.
- The 7.8 percentage point gap between ($P = 180$, pooled) at 87.08% and ($P = 1200$, per-channel) at 94.88% could in principle be carried by either factor, by both, or by interaction.

A controlled ablation isolating P and per-channel binning, holding all other axes fixed, is the right next step and is listed under follow-on work.

3.3 Cell budget vs cell utilization

Cell counts vary across the protocol from 102.5M to 154.2M, because Q and S are sized per model to fit `target_cells` given the model’s module count and channel widths. Cell count does not predict coverage. The two smallest grids in the table (`bloomz-560m` and `bloom-560m` at 102.5M cells) are at 94.32 and 95.91 percent coverage respectively. The largest grid (`qwen7b` at 154.2M cells) is at 94.15 percent coverage. The smaller grids are not less covered; coverage is set by the protocol, not by the budget.

4 Implementation notes

4.1 Module discovery

The probing tool registers forward hooks on every `nn.Linear` and HuggingFace `pytorch_utils.Conv1D` submodule reachable on a single forward pass. When `include_norms` is set, normalization layers (LayerNorm, RMSNorm) are also hooked. Discovery happens at model load time and the module list is cached.

GPT-2 uses `Conv1D` rather than `nn.Linear` for attention and MLP projections; the protocol detects both. Failure to detect `Conv1D` was an early bug in our pipeline and is the kind of silent miss that drops `module_count` and therefore reduces effective channel width.

4.2 Quantile edge memory

For a 7B model with roughly 200 hooked modules and 4096 average channel width, per-channel edges at $Q = 10$ require approximately $200 \times 4096 \times 11$ floats = 9M floats = 36 MB at fp32. This is negligible. Pooled binning saves a factor of 4096 in edge memory but loses coverage.

4.3 Heterogeneous workers

In our runs, calibration was performed on a single host with enough RAM to hold the model in bfloat16. Heat-fill shards were distributed across heterogeneous local nodes:

- One x86 Linux host (24-core CPU, 188 GB DRAM)
- Two Apple Silicon nodes (M4 Pro, 24 GB unified memory; M4, 16 GB unified memory)
- One NVIDIA ARM-GPU workstation (unified memory, 121 GB) for runs that fit in the GPU portion
- A remote archive node serving as merge host and storage

A larger model like Qwen-7B at 7.6B parameters bfloat16 (about 15 GB weights) cannot run heat-fill on the 16 GB Apple Silicon node in fp32; we used bfloat16 throughout to keep the per-worker memory footprint manageable.

4.4 Merge

Shard merge uses element-wise addition. A dedicated host loads each shard’s `grid.npy` as memory-mapped `uint32`, accumulates into a single tensor, and writes the result alongside aggregate metadata. Because heat counts are bounded above by $P \times (S \times \text{heat} - \text{fill} - \text{count})$ per cell, `uint32` is sufficient for all probe configurations we have used; we have not yet encountered overflow.

4.5 Reproducibility constraints

All shards for a given model must use:

- The same model weights (identical safetensors blobs).
- The same probes file (identical bytes).
- The same Q , S , and `include_norms` settings.
- The same `dtype`.
- The same `quantile_edges.npz`.

Heterogeneity in any of these breaks additivity. Our merging script validates the first three by hashing inputs and refusing to combine shards with mismatched parameters.

5 Cost and time

5.1 Calibration

Calibration is one forward pass per probe. For Phi-2 (2.7B) at $P = 1200$, calibration completed in approximately one hour on a 24-core x86 CPU host. For Qwen-7B on the ARM-GPU workstation, calibration completed in approximately fifteen minutes.

5.2 Heat fill

Heat-fill is also one forward pass per probe, plus per-channel quantile digitization. Per-channel digitization adds roughly 10 percent wall time over pooled. For a 7B model on a single CPU worker at $P = 1200$, heat-fill is multiple hours; with four shards across four workers, each worker

handles 300 probes and finishes in approximately one hour.

5.3 Merge

Merge is a sequential element-wise add and runs in seconds for 100M-cell grids on a single core.

5.4 Resource sufficient condition

If a single worker has enough RAM to load the model and produce a 100M-cell `uint32` grid (approximately 400 MB), and at least one machine can execute the calibration pass, the protocol completes. For the runs reported in this paper, CPU execution was feasible at every model size we attempted when RAM was sufficient; GPU acceleration primarily reduced wall-clock time rather than enabling otherwise impossible runs. We have not tested scales beyond 7.6B; at larger sizes the RAM-only path may become impractical.

6 Discussion

6.1 What the protocol does not give

Our protocol produces a coverage-qualified observation grid. It does not produce mechanistic claims about what the model is doing. Coverage means cells were incremented. Interpretation of which cells fire under which inputs is downstream of the grid and is not addressed in this paper.

Sparsity discovery is also out of scope. Channels that are dead in a model will remain dead under any protocol. What our pipeline can tell us, by closing the protocol-induced coverage gap, is which dead channels are model properties rather than sampling artifacts.

6.2 Comparison to alternative approaches

Existing mechanistic interpretability tooling (TransformerLens, NNsight) provides hooks and interventions at high precision but does not prescribe a dense grid protocol or a coverage qualification criterion. Probing studies tend to report per-layer or per-head summaries rather than per-channel heat. Our protocol is complementary: it produces a dense substrate that those higher-level tools can be applied to.

6.3 Limitations

1. We did not run a controlled A/B isolating the per-channel quantile factor from the $P = 1200$ factor. The high-coverage runs use both. The single ($Q = 6, S = 15, P = 180$, pooled) data point on Qwen-3B suggests that the two factors are not jointly necessary, but does not say which factor matters more in the general case. Until the ablation is run, claims about the protocol should be read as joint claims about the (per-channel + $P = 1200$) configuration, not as separate claims about either axis.
2. Models above 8B parameters are not yet represented in our qualified set. Coverage behavior at 12B+ may shift if memory pressure forces shorter probes or smaller batch sizes.
3. Per-channel digitization with $Q \ll \text{channel} - \text{cardinality}$ may still under-resolve channels whose true activation distribution is heavy-tailed; we have not characterized this.
4. The probe corpus ($P = 1200$) is fixed across runs. A model trained on a domain not represented in the probes may report artificially low coverage in modules specific to that domain.
5. Determinism settings (torch deterministic algorithms, math kernel) were not pinned. Coverage values may shift by fractions of a percentage point between repeated runs on the same

hardware.

7 Reproducibility

- Fullgrid observation tooling: probe runner, calibration pass, heat-fill pass, and additive shard merge script.
- Distributed and single-GPU runbooks.
- Per-run output directory containing `meta.json`, `grid.npy`, and `quantile_edges.npz`.
- Aggregate summary file consolidating per-run metadata across all hosts.
- Probes corpus file `probes_1200.txt` used for both calibration and heat-fill passes.

Exact paths, run identifiers, and the tool source are available on request.

Conceptually the pipeline is three steps. Concrete command-line invocations are omitted from the public draft and available alongside the tool release.

1. **Calibration pass:** forward each of P probes through the model with hooks attached, collect per-channel activation samples (capped by a configurable per-module row budget), compute per-channel quantile edges, and write `quantile_edges.npz`.
2. **Heat-fill pass** (optionally sharded over probe subsets): forward each probe again, digitize each (module, channel) activation against the stored edges, increment heat counts in a `uint32` grid of shape (modules, channels, Q , S).
3. **Merge:** for each shard, load `grid.npy` and accumulate element-wise into a final `uint32` grid. The merge step validates that all shards share identical model, probes corpus, Q , S , `dtype`, `include-norms` setting, and quantile edges (via hash comparison) and refuses to merge mismatched shards.

Inputs that must be byte-identical across all shards of a single model are: model weights (safetensors blobs), probes file, Q , S , `include-norms`, `dtype`, and `quantile_edges.npz`. The merge script enforces this by hashing.

8 Follow-on work

Listed in order of urgency:

1. **Per-channel vs P ablation.** Hold the model fixed (Qwen-3B and one BLOOM variant). Run four configurations: (pooled, $P = 180$), (pooled, $P = 1200$), (per-channel, $P = 180$), (per-channel, $P = 1200$). Report coverage for all four. This is the controlled experiment that the present draft cannot answer.
2. Scale-out to 12B+ models. Run the protocol on Mistral-Nemo-12B, Codestral-22B, and a 70B class model. Verify that the qualification threshold (90% coverage at ≥ 100 M cells) holds at scale.
3. Per-channel resolution sensitivity. Sweep Q at fixed P and per-channel binning to find the Q below which coverage drops; this will give a guideline for budget allocation on larger models.
4. Domain sensitivity. Replace the $P = 1200$ corpus with a domain-shifted corpus (e.g., medical text only) and report coverage. The expected effect is reduced coverage in modules specialized for the absent domain.
5. Determinism profile. Run the same protocol twice on the same hardware with deterministic

algorithms enabled; report the coverage variance.

9 Acknowledgments

This work used a heterogeneous distributed compute substrate spanning Linux x86 hosts, Apple Silicon nodes, and one NVIDIA ARM-GPU workstation, coordinated over a private mesh VPN with a remote archive node serving as merge host. Additional Apple Silicon nodes contributed probe shard execution. The probe corpus consists of synthetic, public-domain, and internally generated prompts.